

Holistic, interconnected approaches for the planet's well-being

Change Maker

September 25, 2024

[BOOK REVIEW]

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 Changemaker
★★★★★ Verified Purchase

It's a valuable read for anyone interested in merging science and economics

Reviewed in the United States on September 25, 2024

Better Economics for the Earth by Quan-Hoang Vuong offers a fresh perspective on how quantum and information theories can reshape our understanding of economics, especially in relation to environmental issues. The book simplifies complex scientific concepts and connects... [See more](#)

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Screenshot. A Review of “[Better Economics for the Earth](#)” by ChangeMaker. Reviewed in the United States on September 25, 2024 [1].

Better Economics for the Earth by Quan-Hoang Vuong [and Minh-Hoang Nguyen] offers a fresh perspective on how quantum and information theories can reshape our understanding of economics, especially in relation to environmental issues [2].

The book simplifies complex scientific concepts and connects them to real-world challenges, such as sustainability and resource management. I found it both thought-provoking and accessible, even without a deep background in physics or economics.

The book by Vuong [and Nguyen] encourages readers to rethink traditional economic models and consider more holistic, interconnected approaches for the planet's well-being.

It's a valuable read for anyone interested in merging science and economics to better protect the Earth.

(*) *Note:* This column reprints ChangeMaker's review appearing on the Amazon page of the title: <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/R1TK5GROVEFXLB/>, with some light edits for clarity and fitting our house style.

References

[1] Change Maker. (2024). It's a valuable read for anyone interested in merging science and economics. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/R1TK5GROVEFXLB/>

[2] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH. (2024). *Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/BOD98L5K44>

